

THE AMMOXENIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The Ammoxenidae is a small family known only from Southern Africa and Australia and contains only four genera and 18 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). In South Africa, two genera and nine species, are listed on the National Species List. Six *Ammoxenus* species are listed but according to a unpublished study at least 11 new species have been recognized.

The smaller *Rastellus* is known from only three species. The distribution and behaviour of most ammoxenid species are well recorded and the National Collection of Arachnida house >1392 specimens. Seven known species are listed as Least Concern and two, *Ammoxenus daedalus* Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980 and *Rastellus florisbad* Platnick & Griffin, 1990 is Data Deficient. *Ammoxenus coccineus* Simon, 1893 and *Rastellus kariba* Platnick & Griffin, 1990 are not yet listed in the World Spider Catalog for South Africa.

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Ammoxenus amphalodes female diving Photo P. Webb

FAMILY AMMOXENIDAE Simon, 1893

The Ammoxenidae is a small family known only from Southern Africa and Australia and contains only four genera and 18 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). In South Africa they are represented by two genera and nine species.

COMMON NAMES: Termite Feeding Spiders/ Sand Dvers.

MORPHOLOGY: Very small to medium-sized (1.3-10 mm); two-clawed; ecribellate; entelegyne; eight-eyed spiders; chelicerae modified for burrowing; median spinnerets set slightly forward; anterior spinnerets without piriform gland spigots; posterior median eyes irregular in shape. The two genera differ in shape and size.

In *Ammoxenus* body size: 3–9 mm; male slightly smaller. Colour blackish-brown to pale yellow with abdominal pattern varying from shiny, blackish-brown with pale median band and border, to yellowish with dark transverse patterns; carapace slightly longer than wide, narrower in front, extending to form a horizontal clypeus; chelicerae modified, with main portion curving downwards, with numerous obtuse spines; eyes eight in two rows in a compact group on a small protuberance; abdomen oval, covered with dense, recumbent, plumose setae; leg formula 4321; tarsi are long, flexible, pseudo-segmented, and curled up in dead specimens (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

In *Rastellus* body size: 1.5–3 mm. Colour pale yellow without abdominal pattern, legs similar to body; carapace slightly longer than wide, cephalic region high; chelicerae modified, with a distal rastelliform digging scoop; eyes: eight in two narrow, compact rows; abdomen oval, covered with dense plumose setae; leg formula 4123 (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Platnick & Griffin 1990).

LIFESTYLE: They are specialist termite feeders and are usually found in areas where termites, especially harvester termites of the genera *Hodotermes*, *Microhodotermes* and *Psammotermes* occur (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014; Haddad et al. 2016; Petráková et al. 2015).

In *Rastellus*, the spiders initially dive into the sand to a shallow depth, gathering a small amount of sand with the digging scoops on the chelicerae, which project forward. They then turn around, back up, and lay strands of silk on the sand. They turn around again, and using the digging scoop, push sand to the surface. They excavate a burrow 4–6 cm deep, and line it with silk. Their retreats have been found near *Psammotermes* termite nests (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Den Berg 2010).

Ammoxenus amphalodes female from Irene Photos: Peter Webb

Rastellus kariba female microscope images Photo ASD

AMMOXENIDAE (continued)

TAXONOMY: Simon (1893) described the genus and two species were added Simon (1896 and 1910). The next report on the *Ammoxenus* was by Benoit (1972) in which he described a new species. Dippenaar & Meyer (1980) added information and described two new species. As part of a MSc thesis Bird (2003) revised the genus and added a possible 11 new species but results still to be published. The genus *Rastellus* was described by Platnick & Griffin (1990) and two species from South Africa was recognized. Haddad (2003) describe the female of a third species and Lotz (1996) added the description of a male.

Key to the genera of the Ammoxenidae in South Africa

1. Very small, not larger than 3 mm; uniformly pale in colour; chelicerae with tongue-shaped digging scoop at distal end (a-c)*Rastellus*

- Larger, usually more than 3 mm; body with contrasting patterns; chelicerae with obtuse digging spines (d-f)*Ammoxenus*

Ammoxenus pentheri female feeding on a harvester termite Photo M de Jager

GENUS AMMOXENUS Simon, 1893

The genus contains six widespread species endemic to Southern Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). The northernmost record being from Zambia. Bourass et al. (2014) reported on a single specimen from Libya but it is a doubtful identification.

COMMON NAME: Ammoxenus Termite Feeding Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Ammoxenus coccineus* Simon, 1893.

MORPHOLOGY: Size 3-10 mm. Members of this genus are recognised by the modified chelicerae that bear hornlike setae, form an extension of the clypeus before curving downwards, and are covered with numerous obtuse spines. The legs in dead specimens curl up. The colour pattern varies greatly between specimens of the same species. Two main colour patterns are recognised: a glossy shiny one or a dull coloured one. The carapace is anteriorly narrowed and decorated with two bands. The abdomen is dark with a median band, or pale with a median band with dull chevrons. Male similar to female in shape and size only colour may vary (Dippenaar & Meyer 1980)

LIFESTYLE: The genus is well studied, with several papers published on their behaviour. *Ammoxenus* species also known as sand-divers or termite-feeders are specialist predators of harvester termites. They are free-living soil dwellers (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 1996b) usually found in the soft soil dumps left after excavation by the termites in close proximity to the nest entrance. They are extremely fast-moving spiders that travel rapidly over the soil surface moving between foraging termites and even entering tunnels of termite nests (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman 1991). When disturbed they have the ability to dive head first into sand. They actively prey on selectively-chosen termites, kill them, and then drag them into loose sand where they submerge themselves before eating them (Dean 1988; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1996a; Petráková et al. 2015; Wilson & Clark, 1977). During inactive periods, *Ammoxenus* is found concealed in a sac-like retreat made in soil heaps (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Harris 2005; Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2010). Small, drum-like egg sacs are concealed with the spider in the soil heaps (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1996a,b; Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2010).

TAXONOMY: The first revision on the genus was published by Benoit (1972) followed by a paper by Dippenaar & Meyer (1980) in which they described two new species. Bird (2003) revised the genus as part of her MSc study in which she recognize six new species but results of study is not yet published.

Ammoxenidae. *Ammoxenus* (a-d), a: female, dorsal view; b: carapace, lateral view; c: spinnerets, ventral view; d: male palp, lateral view (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997)

Ammoxenus amphalodes Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980

COMMON NAME: Common Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1980 from Pongola, Farm Vergeval, district Ngotsche, KwaZulu-Natal (Dippenaar & Meyer 1980). The species is widespread occurring in six of the nine provinces (EOO= 295 541 km²; AOO=140 km²; 54-2 302masl). Due to the wide geographical range and absence of known threats, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Free running ground dwellers that live in sand mounds left by *Hodotermes mossambicus* termites. They are very agile and when disturbed they dive head first into the sand (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014). They prey on harvester termites and are usually more abundant in areas where termites (*H. mossambicus* and *Psamotermes* spp.) occur (Petráková et al. 2015; Wilson & Clark, 1977). *A. amphalodes* is a univoltine species with a wide reproductive period corresponding to the seasonal occurrence of termites. The activity density of *A. amphalodes* was tightly coupled to the activity density of *H. mossambicus*, but not to that of *T. trinervoides*. These data provide further evidence that *A. amphalodes* is a monophagous true predator (Haddad et al. 2016). They are easily sampled with pitfall traps and occur in the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Savanna (Foord et al. 2011), Nama-Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes. Specimens were also found inhabiting abandoned mounds of the snouted harvester termite *Trinervitermes trinervoides* (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006; Petráková et al. 2015) in the Free State. They are not common in crops and were only sampled from cotton fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: Free State: Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein (Spesbona) (-29.07, 26.15); Bothaville (-27.38, 26.62); Bothaville (Kromvlei/Rusthoek) (-27.31, 26.74); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Kroonstad (-27.65, 27.24); Vredefort (Rheboksfontein) (-27.05, 27.37); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Abe Bailey Nature Reserve (-26.36, 27.40); Bryanston (-26.046, 28.023; Hartbeesfontein (-26.76, 26.39); Heidelberg -26.5, 28.36; Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Norscott Koppies Nature Reserve (-26.20, 28.04); Midrand, Waterfall (-25.95, 28.14); Randburg (-26.1, 27.92); Knoppieslaagte (-29.95, 27.97); Irene veld at Gem Village (-25.868, 28.218).

Ammoxenus amphalodes male Photo P. Webb

Female diving Photo P. Webb

Ammoxenus amphalodes female Photo P. Webb

Ammoxenus amphalodes male palp after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

Epigynum after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

Ammoxenus amphalodes female epigynum ASD

Ammoxenus amphalodes (continued)

Limpopo: Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas)(-24.56, 28.46); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pietersburg (-23.89, 29.46); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Marble Hall (-25.00, 29.29); Waterberg (Vyeboompoort) (-24.33, 28.33); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Vhembi Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.1426, 29.9266). **North West:** Kroondal (-25.8, 27.32). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pongola (Farm Vergeval, 11 km SSE) (-27.35, 31.61); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.544, 32.155). **Mpumalanga:** Piet Retief (-27.00, 30.79).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Due to the wide geographical range and absence of known threats no conservation actions are recommended. Published records of the species are available from: Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Nylsvlei Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Rietondale Research Station (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman 1991) and Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Habitat where species were sampled at Rietondale

Egg sacs Photo C. Cilliers

Ammoxenus amphalodes male in action Photo P. Webb

Ammoxenus amphalodes female in action Photo P. Webb

Ammoxenus coccineus Simon, 1893

COMMON NAME: Desert Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic species described by Simon (1893) with type locality given only as “Afrique austral”. The species is recorded from four Southern African countries. It is widespread in South Africa, occurring in four of the nine provinces (EOO=504 419 km²; AOO=104 km²; 376-140 masl). Due to its wide geographical range and absence of threats, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: These free running ground spiders live in sand mounds left by termites (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg 2010). They prey on termites, and when disturbed they dive head first into the sand. Found in areas where harvester termites are active. Easily sampled with pitfall traps from the Forest, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Nama Karoo (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2005); and Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) biomes. They were also recorded from cabbage fields and pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Haddad et al. 2005).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zambia, Namibia, Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Mpumalanga:** Goedehoop Forest (-30.07, 23.07); Nelshoogte Forest Reserve (-25.83, 30.83). **Northern Cape:** Bingap 184 (-28.90, 22.98); 70 km SE Kakamas (-28.12, 20.27); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Langberg 138 (-28.92, 24.60); 10 km from Hopetown, Belmont (-29.61, 24.02); 4 km W of Hopetown (-29.62, 24.02); Coboop dunes (-28.75, 19.35); Groblershoop (Farm Koedoesnek (-28.81, 22.53); Strydenburg (-29.95, 23.68); Green Valley Nuts Estate Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Calvinia (Gifkop 166) (-29.95, 19.40); Kenhardt (Swartduinkop) (-29.40, 19.92); Uitsig farm (-27.2, 22.37); Oryx Game Farm (-28.419, 22.175); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.3, 22.44). **North West:** Molopo, near Vostershoop (-25.75, 22.95); Vorsterhoop (-25.84, 23.02). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West Farm 394 (-32.96, 23.67); Beaufort Wes Farm de Pannen (-32.69, 23.43); Beaufort Wes Farm Eerste Water (-32.69, 22.96); Beaufort Wes Farm Nuwerjaarsfontein (-32.57, 23.23); Beaufort Wes Farm Juriesfontein (-32.53, 23.43); Beaufort Wes Farm Groot Kraanvogelfontein (-32.92, 23.64); Beaufort Wes Farm Katdoornkuil (-33.19, 23.26).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Due to its wide geographical range and absence of threats, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern. Protected in three reserves: Nelshoogte Forest Reserve, Benfontein Nature Reserve and Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Dippenaar & Meyer (1980). Known from both sexes.

Ammoxenus coccineus female Photo Les Oates

Ammoxenus coccineus male Photo Les Oates

Male palp Photo T.Bird

Epigynum after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

Female epigynum Photo ASD

Ammoxenus daedalus Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980

COMMON NAME: Dendron Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS : DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic species described by Dippenaar & Meyer (1980) from Dendron in Limpopo. The species is presently known only from two records in the Limpopo Province (EOO= 8km²; AOO 8 km²; 969-1025 masl). Bird (2003) suggested that the species is a junior synonym of *A. psammodromus*. Therefore listed as DDT until the revision is published.

LIFE STYLE: These free running ground spiders live in sand mounds left by termites. They prey on termites and when disturbed they dive head first into the sand. This species was sampled in high number (>400 specimens) from pitfall traps on the farm Amsterdam in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011). At Louis Trichard observed feeding on *Hodotermes* termites (Wilson & Clarke, 1977).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo* : Farm Amsterdam, 16 km NE of Dendron (-23.37, 29.32); Louis Trichardt (-23.04, 29.91).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Presently not recorded from a protected areas and more sampling is needed to determine the status of the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Ammoxenus daedalus female Photo Les Oates

Male palp after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

Epigynum after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

Ammoxenus kalaharicus Benoit, 1972

COMMON NAME: Kalahari Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS : LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic species described by Benoit (1972) from Botswana. In South Africa recorded from two provinces. The species has a wide geographical range in South Africa (EOO= 82 601 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 77-1850 masl). Due to its wide geographical range and absence of threats, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is very abundant in the Cederberg Wilderness Area where they were sampled with pitfall traps from different altitudes (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). Found in the Fynbos and Succulent Karoo biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73). **Western Cape:** Piketberg (Lang Vlei 102) (-32.75, 18.5); Porterville (-32.99, 18.99); Prince Albert (Tierberg) (-33.85, 22.05); Stellenbosch (-33.93 18.85); Brand(-se(-Baai(-31.42, 18.01); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB5.1, 643 m a.s.l. (-32.3958, 19.0873); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB5.2, 677 m a.s.l. (-32.397, 19.087); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB5.3, 680 m a.s.l. (-32.4004, 19.0915); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB5.4, 664 m a.s.l. (-32.4011, 19.0905); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB7.1, 1152 m a.s.l. (-32.4607, 19.2395); Cederberg, Aan Het Berg, CIB2.1, 251 m a.s.l. (-32.2767, 18.5305); Cederberg, Aan Het Berg, CIB2.2, 257 m a.s.l. (-32.2754, 18.5307); Cederberg, Aan Het Berg, CIB2.3, 258 m a.s.l. (-32.2771, 8.52986); Cederberg, Aan Het Berg, CIB2.4, 251 m a.s.l. (-32.2774, 18.5308); Cederberg, Driehoek, CIB6.2, 919 m a.s.l.(-32.4241, 19.1627); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, CIB4.1, 527 m a.s.l. (-32.3495, 19.0071); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, CIB4.3, 551 m a.s.l.(-32.349, 19.006); Cederberg, Sneekop, CIB11.3, 1919 m a.s.l.(-32.3551, 19.1616); Cederberg, Sneekop, CIB13.2, 1531 m a.s.l. (-32.3472,19.1719); Cederberg, Wupperthal, CIB17.1, 522 m a.s.l. (-32.2795, 19.2192); Cederberg, Wupperthal, CIB17.2, 531 m a.s.l.(-32.2802, 19.2198); Cederberg, Wupperthal, CIB17.3, 515 m a.s.l. (-32.2793,19.220);Cederberg, Wupperthal, CIB17.3, 515 m a.s.l.(-32.2793, 19.220); Cederberg, Wupperthal, CIB17.4, 524 m a.s.l. (-32.2779,19.2193).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: It receives some protection in the Cederberg Wilderness Area where it is sampled from several areas (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised Dippenaar & Meyer (1980), known from only the female.

Ammoxenus kalaharicus female Photo Les Oates

Epigynum Photo ASD

Epigynum after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

Ammoxenus pentheri Simon, 1896

COMMON NAME: Pentheri's Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS : LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic species described by Simon (1896) from Botswana. The species is also recorded from South Africa from four provinces (EOO= 26 9921 km²; AOO= 120 km²; 63-1799 masl). Due to its wide geographical range and absence of threats, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: This free running ground spiders live in sand mounds left by termites. Very fast moving and when disturbed they dive head first into the sand. They prey on termites and are found in areas where the harvester termites are active. They were sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Savanna (Foord et al. 2011), Succulent and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Cradock (-32.16, 25.16); Kirkwood (Dunbrody, nr. Blue Cliff) (-33.38, 25.45); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Jansenville: Farm Osplaas 20 km NWW (-32.88, 24.5); Jansenville Farm Suurhoek (-32.87, 24.47); Jansenville Farm Matjiesfontein (-32.83, 24.44); Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Wellwood 518 (-31.59, 24.58). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Van Reenen Pass (-28.37, 29.38). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (Langberg) (-29.92, 24.60); Victoria West (-31.40, 23.12); Colesberg (Farm Vogelsfontein 71) (-30.62, 25.30). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (Lammetjieslaagte) (-32.18, 22.19); Ashton (-33.83, 20.06); Willowmore (-33.30, 23.30); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); Beaufort West (Farm 151b) (-32.32, 23.45); Beaufort West, (Farm Eerste Water) (-32.69, 22.96); Beaufort West, (Farm De Pannen) (-32.69, 23.43); Beaufort West, (Farm Nuwejaarsfontein) (-32.57, 23.23); Beaufort West, (Farm 394) (-32.96, 23.67); Beaufort West, (Farm Klaarstroom) (-33.33, 22.54); Beaufort West, Prince Albert (Farm Botterkraal) (-33.11, 22.31); Beaufort West, Prince Albert (Tierberg) (-33.85, 22.05); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Cederberg, Wupperthal, 531 m a.s.l. (-32.280, 19.2198); Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.3443, 20.5051).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in six protected areas. This include three national parks: Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006); Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020) and Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 1999) as well as the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised Dippenaar & Meyer (1980); known from both sexes.

Ammoxenus pentheri female feeding Photo M de Jager

Palp Photo T. Bird

Ammoxenus pentheri female Photo Les Oates

Epigynum after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

Female epigynum Photo ASD

Ammoxenus psammodromus Simon, 1910

COMMON NAME: Sand loving Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic that was described by Simon (1910) from Botswana in 1910. It has also been recorded from Namibia and four provinces in South Africa (EOO= 184 253 km²; AOO= 72 km²; 605-1345 masl). Due to its wide geographical range and absence of threats, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: These free running ground spiders live in sand mounds left by termites. Very fast moving and when disturbed they dive head first into the sand. They prey on termites and are abundant in areas where the harvester termites are active. They were sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Nama Karoo and Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Willowmore (-33.30, 23.30). **Free State:** Boshof (Farm Elliesdal 1062) (-28.8, 25.52); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Jacobsdal, Kimberley Rd. (-29.18, 24.77); Brandfort (Krugersdrift Dam) (-28.72, 24.92); Request on Inglswood 1108 (-28.60, 24.85). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam)(-23.37, 29.32); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.949, 29.8696); Louis Trichardt (-22.99, 29.92); Malebogo Nature Reserve, nr. Blouberg (-23.07, 28.88); Soutpansberg, Farm Stoke (-22.483, 29.883); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm BRI 1 (-23.176, 29.764); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm BRI 2 (-23.178, 29.772); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm BRI 3 (-23.175, 29.769); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm BRI 4(-23.169, 29.771); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm BRI 5 (-23.1654, 29.772); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm (-23.1658, 29.776); Vhembi Biosphere Bristow Farm (-23.170, 29.780); Vhembi Biosphere Mashovelo Lodge (-22.937, 29.895); Vhembi Biosphere Mashovelo Lodge (-22.943, 29.882). **North West:** Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73); Table (Farm 247) (-28.72, 24.92).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in two reserve: Blouberg (Foord et al. 2019) and Malebogo. Species was also commonly found at Little Leigh in the Western Soutpansberg (Muelelwa et al. 2011). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised, and known from both sexes.

Ammoxenus psammodromus female Photo P. Webb

Palp Photo T. Bird

Epigynum Photo ASD

Epigynum after Dippenaar & Meyer (1980)

GENUS *RASTELLUS* Platnick & Griffin, 1990

The genus contains seven species endemic to Southern Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). The northernmost record being from Botswana. Three species are known from the atlas region.

COMMON NAME: Lesser Termite Feeding Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Rastellus africanus* Platnick & Griffin, 1990

MORPHOLOGY: Small spiders (2–3 mm). Body pale yellow, without markings, except tip of darker chelicerae and eye region. Carapace in cephalic region convex, oval in dorsal view, widest between coxae II and III, truncated anteriorly and posteriorly; eyes in circular arrangement, with posterior median eyes large; chelicerae provided with distal, rastelliform digging scoop. Abdomen and legs are similar in colour to carapace. Legs of medium length. Male similar to female (Platnick & Griffin, 1990; Dippenaar et al. 2013)

LIFE STYLE: *Rastellus* species are ground living spiders. They are adapted to life in sandy habitats. The rastelliform digging scoop is used for digging in sand. Most known specimens were taken in pitfall traps in sandy habitats. Extensive hand searching has been unsuccessful in locating additional specimens, and the spiders probably spend most of their time buried under the sand surface. They are frequently sampled in pitfall traps indicating that they wander around (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg (2010); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad (2014);

TAXONOMY: The genus was described by Platnick & Griffin (1990) followed by papers by Lotz (1996) and Haddad (2003).

Rastellus sp. female lateral view Photo ASD

Rastellus sp. spinnerets Photo ASD

Rastellus sp. female chelicerae Photo ASD

Rastellus sp. female ventral view Photo ASD

Rastellus deserticola Haddad, 2003

COMMON NAME: Desert Lesser Termite-Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Haddad (2003) from the from the Green Valley Nuts farm, Prieska in the Northern Cape in South Africa. It is also recorded from Namibia. In South Africa known from two provinces (EOO= 678 080 km²; AOO= 56 km²; 243-1850 masl). Due to the geographical range the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: These free-living ground dwellers are adapted to life in sandy habitats. They excavate and line a burrow 4-6 cm deep with silk. Their excavations have been found near termite nests. They have also been collected with termites in dead wood laying on the ground. They are sometimes sampled in pitfall traps, indicating that they wander around. Adult *R. deserticola* were only active in spring and early summer during a year of pitfall trapping (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Den Berg 2010). Specimens were also collected from pitfall traps in Nama Karoo grassland in the Prieska district (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2005)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.58,22.93); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Oryx Game Farm (-28.4192, 22.1748). **Western Cape:** Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1179 m a.s.l. (-32.4564, 19.2368); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1337 m a.s.l. (-32.43470, 19.2157); Cederberg, Aan Het Berg, 251 m a.s.l. (-32.2767, 18.5305); Cederberg, Aan Het Berg, 258 m a.s.l. (-32.2771, 18.52986); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, 1133 m a.s.l. (-32.3322, 19.1410); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, 934 m a.s.l. (-32.31095, 19.1706); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, 927 m a.s.l. (-32.3107, 19.1723); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, 927 m a.s.l. (-32.3104, 19.1740); Cederberg, Driehoek, 919 m a.s.l. (-32.4241, 19.1627); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, 527 m a.s.l. (-32.350, 19.007); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, 565 m a.s.l. (-32.3482, 19.0048); Cederberg, Sawadee, 385 m a.s.l. (-32.3373, 18.9911); Cederberg, Sawadee, 344 m a.s.l. (-32.338, 18.988); Cederberg, Sneekop, 1605 m a.s.l. (-32.3554, 19.1525); Cederberg, Sneekop, 1843 m a.s.l. (-32.3555, 19.1654); Cederberg, Sneekop, 1669 m a.s.l. (-32.3538, 19.1678); Cederberg, Wupperthal, 522 m a.s.l.(-32.2795, 19.2192); Cederberg, Wupperthal, 531 m a.s.l. (-32.2802, 19.2, 198); Cederberg, Wupperthal, 515 m a.s.l. (-32.2793, 19.220); Cederberg, Wupperthal, 524 m a.s.l. (-32.2779, 19.2193).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species receives protection in the Benfontein Game Reserve and are abundant in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Rastellus deserticola female dorsal and ventral view
Photo ASD

Epigynum Photo ASD

Epigynum after Haddad (2003)

Rastellus deserticola female anterior view Photo ASD

Rastellus florisbad Platnick & Griffin, 1990

COMMON NAME: Florisbad Lesser Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Platnick & Griffin (1990), from the type locality Florisbad in the Free State. The species was also sampled from KwaZulu-Natal. Several specimens were sampled from the two known localities (EOO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 140-1283 masl). Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

LIFE STYLE: A very small free-living ground dweller that is adapted to life in sandy habitats (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014). The species has been sampled with pitfall traps from the Grassland (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014; Haddad et al. 2013); and Savanna biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State:* Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.08); *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.54444, 32.15461).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species receives some protection in the Florisbad Research Station as well as the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Rastellus florisbad female dorsal and ventral view ASD

Epigynum after Lotz (1996).

Rastellus florisbad male palp and epigynum ASD

Rastellus kariba Platnick & Griffin, 1990

COMMON NAME: Kariba Lesser Termite Feeding Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: Southern African endemic described Platnick & Griffin (1990), from Zimbabwe. The species has also been sampled from Botswana and South Africa. In South Africa it was sampled from several localities in the Limpopo Province. (EOO= 55 122 km²; 32 km²; 238-1528 masl). The species has a wide geographical distribution and is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: A very small free-living ground spider that is adapted to life in sandy habitats. They are frequently sampled in pitfall traps indicating that they wander around.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, South Africa, Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Thabazimbi Acacia Game Lodge (-24.60, 27.38); Kruger National Park (5 km N of Letaba Camp) (-23.83, 31.58); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Mussina (-22.33, 30.03); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (-23.141, 29.553); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is protected in two reserves: Blouberg and Makalali Nature Reserves, as well as in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Rastellus kariba female lateral view Photo ASD

Rastellus ariba female chelicerae and carapace Photo ASD

Rastellus kariba abdomen Photo ASD

Rastellus kariba epigynum after Platnick & Griffin (1990).

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